

Full Orchestration of a Distributed 5G cloud-native Mobile Network: O-RAN, Core, and Transport

Jorge Baranda*, Javier Velázquez Martínez[†], Albert Bel*, David Gregoratti[‡],
Luis M. Contreras[†], Josep Mangués-Bafalluy*

* Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Castelldefels, Spain;

[†] Telefonica Innovación Digital / CTIO, Madrid, Spain;

[‡] Software Radio Systems (SRS), Barcelona, Spain

Abstract—Novel networking paradigms based on programmability and softwarization are deeply transforming the architecture and end-to-end management of next-generation mobile networks. This demonstration provides a step beyond in this transformation process by showcasing the full cloud-native deployment of a disaggregated and distributed 5G mobile network from core to Radio Access Network (RAN) using open-source software. The distinguishing features of the proposed approach are that the orchestration process includes the use of a cloud-based Distributed Unit (DU) communicating through O-RAN Split 7.2 with a Radio Unit (RU) performing over-the-air transmission, the end-to-end configuration of slices with on-demand activation of core network function components, and the dynamic configuration of transport network flows to differently route the traffic of active slices.

Index Terms—B5G/6G, NFV/SDN, Slicing, Management and Orchestration, Cloud-Native, O-RAN, Split 7.2, Open5GS, srsRAN, TeraFlow SDN

I. INTRODUCTION

Virtualization/cloudification, softwarization, and the use of open interfaces are transforming the architecture and management of next-generation mobile networks. The adoption of such paradigms are making mobile networks transitioning towards disaggregated networks separating control and user plane network functions (NFs). This trend, started in the Core segment with the Service Based Architecture (SBA), is currently followed in the Radio Access Network (RAN) segment through the propositions of Open RAN (O-RAN) alliance [1]. Thanks to this, mobile networks can be more flexibly deployed to meet the requirements of challenging use cases proposed by vertical industries, include close-loop operations enhancing the performance of the network and promote interoperability among multi-vendor providers. In order to achieve so, it is needed to define appropriate management and orchestration (MANO) procedures of not only mobile network entities but also considering the dynamic configuration of the transport network interconnecting the points of presence (PoPs) where these mobile network entities may be distributed.

This demonstration deals with such MANO procedures to allow the flexible and distributed deployment of a complete

full end-to-end cloud-native mobile network based on open-source software. Regarding the Core segment, there are several recent works presenting cloud-native deployments (i.e., [2], [3]). All of them are based on Open5GS [4] software, but during the deployment process, the distribution of the different NFs of the mobile core is predefined and static in a single Kubernetes cluster, lacking the flexibility to further redefine the deployment by starting them upon demand. Regarding the RAN segment, to the best of our knowledge, examples using a cloud-native approach are more limited (e.g., [5], [6]) and they use Open Air Interface and UERANSIM, differently to this work, which is based on srsRAN [7]. In [6], the authors also deal with the configuration of end-to-end slices, however they use Split 8 transmission and they do not consider the orchestration of transport network resources, which usually are considered in other MANO works (e.g., [8], [9]) for the interconnection of vertical applications hosted in data centers and not for the interconnection of mobile network entities.

In this work, we provide a step beyond in the research on orchestration of mobile networks by showing the first practical implementation of a disaggregated and distributed deployment of a fully end-to-end open-source cloud-native mobile network featuring a configurable number of slices, employing O-RAN Split 7.2 in the RAN segment and considering also the on-demand configuration of transport network flows meeting the requirements of associated active slices. The different mobile network entities are handled as individual Network Services (NSs), thus through an ETSI NFVI MANO platform we achieve automated, flexible, and portable deployments. Through the distribution of the different mobile entities across available PoPs, this MANO system can adapt to the evolving requirements of the network traffic, such as supporting the on-demand creation and deletion of different mobile network entities such as, Session Management Functions (SMFs) and User Plane Functions (UPFs) to activate the mobile entities handling the slice traffic.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows the experimental setup deployed between the xG EXTREME Testbed[®] located in CTTC (Castelldefels, Spain) and the Telefonica Innovation Lab (Madrid, Spain), which are interconnected through a Virtual Private Network (VPN). This setup can be divided into three segments: com-

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Fig. 1. System Architecture under demonstration showing the final distribution of deployed cloud-native mobile network entities.

puting hardware for mobile Core and RAN software, RAN hardware, and transport network. The computing hardware consists of four commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) servers. One server executes our MANO system powered by an instance of ETSI Open Source MANO (OSM). The remaining three servers act as PoPs, each running a single-node Kubernetes cluster. These three clusters mimic the tiers available in an MNO deployment, i.e., central, regional and edge clouds, where the NSs associated with the mobile network entities are dynamically deployed. The RAN-related hardware consists of an O-RAN switch and Precision Time Protocol (PTP) grandmaster, an O-Radio Unit (RU), and two smartphones for over-the-air (OTA) transmissions. More specifically, we employ a Falcon RX/812/G O-RAN switch, a LITEON FlexFi FF-RFI07814 O-RU and, a Realme 9 and a OnePlus 8 Pro smartphones, which are handled via a remote desktop tool (e.g., AnyDesk). The transport network segment consists of two COTS servers, one executing the stack of transport network SDN controllers and another one running EVE-NG software to emulate the transport topology of Cisco XRV9000 routers depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Transport network topology emulated on EVE-NG.

This demonstration shows the capabilities of this setup to

perform the automated orchestration of a fully distributed 5G cloud-native mobile network presenting multiple slices, including O-RAN entities using Split 7.2 and OTA transmission. In the transport control part, the orchestration is conducted by our implementation of the Network Slice Controller (NSC), a software-defined controller defined by IETF [13] to orchestrate the request, realization, and lifecycle control of transport network slices. This component processes intents following 3GPP format and converts them to IETF slicing intents [14] to be consumed by the TeraFlow SDN transport controller [15]. In particular, transport slices are realized into Layer 2 VPNs, setting up a *pseudo-wire* associated with one of the tunnels previously established in the topology to route mobile network control and user-plane (CP and UP) traffic flows belonging to different network slices.

Regarding the entities of the mobile network, the setup is based on the blueprints (i.e., Helm Charts) described in [10]. Namely, the 5G Core part is *Open5GS v2.7.1*, and it is deployed through three different blueprints for higher flexibility. One blueprint deploys the CP network functions, the second one allows the deployment of an SMF instance, and the third one allows the deployment of an UPF instance for UP function. The SMF-UPF decoupling allows a flexible activation, upon demand, of dedicated slice components. In the RAN part, we count with two blueprints, one for the Central Unit (CU) and one for the Distributed Unit (DU) using *srsRAN Release 24.12*. The DU manifest is configured to connect to the LITEON FlexFi O-RU hardware through Split 7.2 open fronthaul interface and to launch OTA transmission. Beyond the mobile network entities, an additional blueprint relying on Linux *ptp4l* and *phc2sys* processes is executed to acquire the PTP synchronization provided by the Falcon Switch. The flexible templating capabilities of Helm Charts facilitate the parametrization of blueprints for the mobile core entities, CU, and DU, allowing the deployment of a mobile network with a configurable number of slices and physical RAN-allocation configuration for these slices (e.g., ratio of Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs)). These blueprints are further encapsulated in

OSM descriptors (VNF and NS packages), so the mentioned parametrization can be exploited through OSM instantiation commands, enabling the on-demand and flexible creation of instances of these entities to fit the needs of given scenarios, such as those included in [11]. These Helm charts are publicly available at [12]¹.

III. DEMONSTRATION

This demonstration showcases the orchestration of a fully disaggregated cloud-native open-source 5G mobile network considering Core, transport and RAN segments. The orchestrated network employs Split 7.2 between DU and O-RU and allows the on-demand activation of NFs handling the different slices and associated transport flows, thus enabling the deployment of scenarios covering different requirements in terms of latency and bandwidth. The involved mobile NFs are packaged as different NSs. Initially, these packages are onboarded into the OSM MANO stack and the transport network flow intent templates (CP and UP) are defined. The main steps of the demonstration are as follows:

- 1) We request our MANO system to deploy the PTP artefact in the *edge cloud* to provide the required synchronization between DU and RU to the network interfaces of *edge cloud* connected to the Falcon O-RAN switch.
- 2) OSM receives the request from our MANO system to deploy the Open5GS CP NS in the *central cloud*. We configure two slices for this deployment (i.e., SST:1 and SST:2). Once deployed, the information of the multiple UEs and their slice association are included in the UDR database. Then, we deploy the additional Open5GS NSs (i.e., *SMF1*, *UPF1*) corresponding to slice #1 (i.e., SST:1) also in the *central cloud*. This slice is devoted to low bandwidth and *non-latency sensitive* communications, e.g., machine-type communications.
- 3) Later, we send a request to the NSC to configure the transport network paths to allow the F1 communication for slice#1 (CP interface flow, i.e., *F1-c*, is common for all slices but UP interface flow, i.e., *F1-u1*, belongs to a given slice).
- 4) After that, we deploy the disaggregated RAN components (i.e., CU and DU) in the *edge cloud*. As with core entities, these CU and DU instances are configured to serve two slices. Additionally, we specify the resources (e.g., ratio of PRBs) assigned to each of the requested slices in the DU to fit the requirements of the different slices.
- 5) Then, we register the UE_1 in the network. After leaving flight mode, the UE_1 receives an IP address in the range of the data network associated with slice#1, thanks to the configured CP flow in the transport network. UP communication flows through the path configured for the *F1-u1* flow.
- 6) We request our MANO system to deploy the set of Open5GS NSs for slice#2 (SST:2) (i.e., *SMF2*, *UPF2*) in the *regional cloud*, devoted to high bandwidth and *latency-sensitive* communications.
- 7) After this, we send a request to the NSC to configure the transport network path to allow the F1-u for slice#2, i.e., *F1-u2*. Once this flow is configured in the transport network,

we register UE_2 in the network and its UP traffic will flow through a disjoint transport network path, experiencing different performance according to its different requirements. Throughout the demonstration, each step is visualised using the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of our MANO system, a remote desktop session displaying smartphone activity, and live wireshark captures at key routers showing the packets flowing through each of the three configured transport paths.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this demonstration, we present the full on-demand deployment of an open-source 5G mobile network featuring multiple configurable end-to-end slices and O-RAN Split 7.2 with OTA transmission. The different cloud-native mobile network entities, encompassing Core and RAN functionalities, can be distributed as needed following multiple geographical distributions among available PoPs according to the scenarios proposed by the O-RAN alliance. Our system relies on the creation of descriptors exploiting orchestration tools like OSM and Kubernetes and the NSC, which exploits TeraFlow SDN controller to configure the required flows for the different slices in the transport network interconnecting such PoPs, which is also a distinguishing feature of our system. This approach paves the way for more flexible and efficient end-to-end management and orchestration of B5G/6G mobile networks.

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¹This repository will be made available once this work is accepted.